

CHARGE AND STABILITY OF COLLOIDS. PART II. EFFECT OF NON-ELECTROLYTES

By B. P. YADAVA

The effects of non-electrolytes such as methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol, agar agar, and gelatine have been studied from the view-point of the variation in the adsorption of oppositely charged ions by the colloidal particles of arsenious sulphide and ferric hydroxide sols. It has been observed that the sol is sensitised in the case of methyl alcohol whereas stabilised in the case of other non electrolytes.

Sensitisation of hydrophobic sols by non-electrolytes and specially hydrophilic colloids in low concentrations, is a very general phenomenon. It has also been observed that some non-electrolytes impart stability and specially some of these hydrophilic sols in larger concentrations produce considerable protection.

Various theories have been advanced from time to time to explain the phenomenon of sensitisation and protection. Freundlich and Löning ("Kaiser Wilhelm Gesellschafts-Festschrift," 1921, p. 82) consider that sensitisation is due to the presence of colloidal ions in the lyophilic sols. They suggest that the non-electrolyte is adsorbed on the surface of the colloidal particles. Pauli and Kitaj (*Kolloid Z.*, 1938, 82, 43) explain sensitisation by supposing that an exchange takes place between the oppositely charged groups of the hydrophobic and the hydrophilic colloids.

Both the phenomena, *i.e.* the adsorption suggested by Freundlich and the exchange supposed to take place at the surface of the colloidal particles by Pauli, should lead to the lowering of the charge (*cf.* Weiser, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1924, 28, 1253) and due to this a sensitisation may occur. This is further confirmed by Freundlich assuming that sensitisation takes place when the hydrophobic sol is in excess and the hydrophilic sol must contain colloidal ions with charges opposite to those of the hydrophobic sols. On the other hand, Freundlich says "that protection is due to the adsorption of the hydrophilic sol on the particles of the hydrophobic sol so as to surround the latter and form a layer round it." It follows from this that the protective action certainly does not depend upon a strong charge being communicated to the particle.

It appears from the above, therefore, that when protection takes place the charge on the colloidal particle should not necessarily increase appreciably.

In this paper adsorption of oppositely charged ions by the colloidal particles of arsenious sulphide sol and ferric hydroxide sol has been measured by the method given in Part I of this series of papers (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 20, 25) in presence of various non-electrolytes and hydrophilic colloids in varying concentrations in order to find out how the adsorption varies under different conditions. Under limitations as pointed out in the previous paper of this series (*loc. cit.*) charge on the colloidal particles has been calculated from the amount of "chemical adsorption" alone, on the assumption that at the coagulating concentration of the electrolytes the adsorbed ions displace all ions of the same sign in the double layer.

EXPERIMENTAL

The experimental procedure followed in this paper is the same as the one given in Part I (*loc. cit.*). With arsenious sulphide sol and methyl alcohol a sensitisation has been observed. The coagulating concentrations for a particular sol of known concentration, when methyl alcohol in a given percentage is added to the sol, are given in Table I.

TABLE I

Sol conc. = 16.16 g./litre. Sol taken = 5 c.c. Total volume = 10 c.c.

Methyl alcohol added (% by volume)	...	0	1	10	25
Coagulating conc. of $N/80$ -BaCl ₂ added (c.c.)	...	1.500	1.375	1.250	1.200

In measuring the adsorption with methyl alcohol the results obtained at coagulating concentrations are given in Table II(A). Here we observe that the adsorption decreases. Adsorptions were also measured when the concentration of the electrolyte was greater than the coagulating concentration and the results obtained are given in Table II(B). In this case also it is seen that the adsorption of the oppositely charged ion decreases. In all other cases the coagulating concentrations of the electrolytes have been added both in presence as well as in absence of the non-electrolyte in question. In the above table the percentage by volume has been calculated on the amount of the volume of methyl alcohol to 100 c.c. of the pure sol and not in total volume of the mixture.

The results obtained with arsenious sulphide and ferric hydroxide sols in presence of methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol, agar agar, and gelatine are given in the following tables.

TABLE II

Variation in the adsorption of Ba-ions by the particles of As₂S₃ sol when MeOH added in increasing conc. to it

A. Sol conc. = 16.16 g./litre. Radius of the particle = 75 μ (by extrapolation). Sol taken = 100 c.c. Total vol. = 200 c.c. No. of particles in the sol = 2.574×10^{14} .

B. Sol conc. = 24.18 g./litre. Radius of the particle = 75 μ (by extrapolation). Sol taken = 250 c.c. Total vol. = 500 c.c. No. of particles in the sol = 9.627×10^{14} . The electrolyte added is above coagulating conc.

Nature of sol.	Adsorption of Ba-ions.				Nature of sol.	Adsorption of Ba-ions.					
	N/80-BaCl ₂ added.	Total.	Physical.	Chemical.		Charge (e.s.u. $\times 10^9$).	N/20-BaCl ₂ added.	Total.	Physical.	Chemical.	Charge (e.s.u. $\times 10^9$).
Sol + water	30 c.c.	0.00365 g.	0.00041g.	0.00324 g.	5.31	Sol + water	25.0 c.c.	0.0135 g.	0.0016 g.	0.0119 g.	5.21
Sol + 1.0 c.c. MeOH + H ₂ O	27.5	0.00291	0.000243	0.00267	4.06	Sol + 2.5 c.c. MeOH + H ₂ O	26.0	0.0109	0.0017	0.0092	4.03
Sol + 10 c.c. MeOH + H ₂ O	25.0	0.00273	0.00045	0.00228	3.76	Sol + 5 c.c. MeOH + H ₂ O	26.5	0.0102	0.0017	0.0085	3.72
Sol + 25 c.c. MeOH + H ₂ O	24.0	0.00260	0.00045	0.00215	3.49	Sol + 10 c.c. MeOH + H ₂ O	26.5	0.0099	0.0018	0.0081	3.56
						Sol + 20 c.c. MeOH + H ₂ O	26.5	0.0096	0.0019	0.0077	3.37

From Table II it is clear that the adsorption of oppositely charged ions by the colloidal particles definitely decreases whether we add just the coagulating concentration or above it,

TABLE III

Variation in the adsorption of Ba-ions by the colloidal particles of As_2S_3 sol with increasing concentrations of EtOH and 0.2% agar agar

A. Sol conc. = 24.0 g./litre. Radius of the particles = 75 μ (by extrapolation). Sol taken = 250 c.c. Total vol. = 500 c.c. No. of particles in the sol = 9.557×10^{14} .					B. Sol conc. = 23.75 g./litre. Radius of the particles = 75 μ (by extrapolation). Sol taken = 250 c.c. Total vol. = 500 c.c. No. of particles in the sol = 9.46×10^{14} .						
Nature of sol.	N/100-BaCl ₂ added.	Adsorption of Ba-ions.			Charge (e.s.u. $\times 10^6$).	Nature of sol.	N/100-BaCl ₂ added.	Adsorption of Ba-ions.			Charge (e.s.u. $\times 10^6$).
		Total.	Physical.	Chemical.				Total.	Physical.	Chemical.	
Sol + water	25.0 c.c.	0.0135g.	0.0016g.	0.0119g.	5.25	Sol + water	25.0 c.c.	0.0135g.	0.0016g.	0.0119g.	5.29
Sol + 2.5 c.c. EtOH + H ₂ O	26.0	0.0153	0.0018	0.0135	5.96	Sol + 2.5 c.c. agar + H ₂ O	26.0	0.0145	0.0018	0.0127	5.66
Sol + 5 c.c. EtOH + H ₂ O	26.5	0.0143	0.0019	0.0124	5.47	Sol + 5 c.c. agar + H ₂ O	26.5	0.0140	0.0018	0.0122	5.44
Sol + 10 c.c. EtOH + H ₂ O	26.5	0.0141	0.0019	0.0122	5.38	Sol + 10 c.c. agar + H ₂ O	26.5	0.0137	0.0019	0.0118	5.26
Sol + 20 c.c. EtOH + H ₂ O	26.5	0.0140	0.0020	0.0120	5.29	Sol + 20 c.c. agar + H ₂ O	26.5	0.0134	0.0019	0.0115	5.22

TABLE IV

Sol conc. = 22.76 g./litre. Radius of the particles = 75 μ (by extrapolation). Sol taken = 250 c.c. Total vol. = 500 c.c. No. of the particles in the sol = 9.063×10^{14} . Conc. of the gelatine used = 0.32% by weight.

A. With increasing concentration of unwashed gold label gelatine. B. With increasing concentration of washed iso-electric gelatine.

Nature of sol.	N/100-BaCl ₂ added.	Adsorption of Ba-ions.			Charge (e.s.u. $\times 10^6$).	Nature of sol.	N/100-BaCl ₂ ad ded.	Adsorption of Ba-ions.			Charge in (e.s.u. $\times 10^6$).
		Total.	Physical.	Chemical.				Total.	Physical.	Chemical.	
Sol + water	25.0 c.c.	0.0134g.	0.0016g.	0.0118g.	5.49	Sol + water	25.0 c.c.	0.0134g.	0.0016g.	0.0118g.	5.40
Sol + 2.5 c.c. gelat. + H ₂ O	26.0	0.0137	0.0017	0.0120	5.59	Sol + 2.5 c.c. gelat. + H ₂ O	26.0	0.0136	0.0017	0.0119	5.54
Sol + 5.0 c.c. gelat. + H ₂ O	26.5	0.0136	0.0018	0.0118	5.49	Sol + 5.0 c.c. gelat. + H ₂ O	26.5	0.0134	0.0017	0.0117	5.44
Sol + 10 c.c. gelat. + H ₂ O	26.5	0.0133	0.0019	0.0114	5.30	Sol + 10 c.c. gelat. + H ₂ O	26.5	0.0128	0.0018	0.0110	5.14
Sol + 20 c.c. gelat. + H ₂ O	26.5	0.0130	0.0019	0.0111	5.16	Sol + 20 c.c. gelat. + H ₂ O	26.5	0.0127	0.0019	0.0108	5.02

The concentrations of the sol as well as of the gelatine used in Table IV(B) are exactly the same as those used in Table IV(A).

The following are the results obtained with a positively charged ferric hydroxide sol which was dialysed for about a month. Its purity and concentration are: conc. = 9.104 g./litre; chlorine content of the sol = 0.5484 g./litre; radius of the particles = 50 μ (by extrapolation).

Variation of Adsorption of SO_4 -ions by colloidal $Fe(OH)_3$

TABLE V

Sol taken = 100 c.c. Total vol. = 200 c.c. Number of the particles as calculated in the sol = 4.694×10^{12} .

Nature of sol	A. With increasing conc. of MeOH (pure). Adsorption of SO_4 -ions.					B. With increasing conc. of freshly distilled EtOH. Adsorption of SO_4 -ions.				
	N/20 K_2SO_4 added.	Total.	Physical.	Chemical.	Charge (e.s.u. $\times 10^6$).	N/20 K_2SO_4 added.	Total.	Physical.	Chemical.	Charge (e.s.u. $\times 10^6$).
Sol + water	20'0 c.c.	0'0438 g.	0'00351 g.	0'0403 g.	5'17	20'0 c.c.	0'0438 g.	0'00351 g.	0'0403 g.	5'17
Sol + 1 c.c. ROH + H_2O	21'0	0'0417	0'00353	0'0382	4'92	21'0	0'0490	0'00352	0'0455	5'84
Sol + 10 c.c. ROH + H_2O	22'5	0'0405	0'00356	0'0369	4'73	22'5	0'0483	0'00354	0'0448	5'76
Sol + 20 c.c. ROH + H_2O	22'5	0'0384	0'00358	0'0348	4'47	22'5	0'0477	0'00356	0'0442	5'68
Sol + 40 c.c. ROH + H_2O	22'5	0'0360	0'00359	0'0324	4'16	22'5	0'0473	0'00358	0'0437	5'62

R in A stands for Me and in B for Et.

TABLE VI

Sol taken = 100 c.c. Total vol. = 200 c.c. No. of particles as calc. in the sol = 4.694×10^{12} .

Nature of sol.	A. With increasing conc. of 0'25% of agar agar. Adsorption of SO_4 -ions.					B. With increasing conc. of 0'32% gold label gelatine. Adsorption of SO_4 -ions.				
	N/20 K_2SO_4 added.	Total.	Physical.	Chemical.	Charge (e.s.u. $\times 10^6$).	N/20 K_2SO_4 added.	Total.	Physical.	Chemical.	Charge (e.s.u. $\times 10^6$).
Sol + water	20'0 c.c.	0'0438 g.	0'00351 g.	0'0403 g.	5'17	20'0 c.c.	0'0435 g.	0'00351 g.	0'0403 g.	5'17
Sol + 1 c.c. agar + H_2O	21'0	0'0441	0'00354	0'0406	5'22	21'0	0'0439	0'00352	0'0404	5'19
Sol + 10 c.c. agar + H_2O	22'5	0'0435	0'00355	0'0400	5'14	22'5	0'0429	0'00355	0'0394	5'06
Sol + 20 c.c. agar + H_2O	22'5	0'0427	0'00358	0'0397	5'02	22'5	0'0416	0'00357	0'0380	4'88
Sol + 50 c.c. agar + H_2O	22'5	0'0422	0'00358	0'0386	4'96	22'5	0'0407	0'00359	0'0372	4'77

DISCUSSION

From the results given in Tables II and V(A) it is seen that when methyl alcohol is added to the As_2S_3 and $Fe(OH)_3$ sols there is a slight lowering in the adsorption of the oppositely charged ions. This lowering in the adsorption may explain the sensitisation observed with methyl alcohol by Choudhury (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1928, 28, 1481). In the case of ethyl alcohol it is observed from Tables III(A) and V(B) that the adsorption increases but on adding larger amounts of ethyl alcohol it decreases but still remains greater than that by the original sol. From Tables III(B) and VI(A) it can be observed that in the case of agar agar the adsorption of the oppositely charged ion almost remains constant with a slight tendency to increase in lower concentrations of agar agar but in

higher concentrations it is followed by a slight decrease. From Tables IV and VI(A) it will be seen that with gelatine the adsorption almost remains constant, although there is a slight increase at low concentrations of the gelatine added to the sol, but it has a tendency to decrease when the amount of gelatine added increases. This decreasing tendency is more marked with washed iso-electric gelatine.

It is also interesting to note that with agar agar and various gelatines added there is always a slight increase in the "physical adsorption" on adding the hydrophilic colloid, but it does not increase perceptibly on increasing the quantity of the protective colloid.

Sensitisation has been attributed by various authors to be either due to a change in the physical conditions, such as dielectric constant, interfacial tension, decrease in the degree of hydration etc., or due to a decrease in the electric charge on the colloid by the adsorption of either oppositely charged colloidal ions or interaction between oppositely charged groups of the hydrophobic and the hydrophilic colloids.

When sensitisation is due to a decrease in the electrical charge it is certain that a high concentration of the non-electrolyte is not necessary and therefore non-electrolytes like hydrophilic colloids can produce sensitisation due to charge neutralisation, whereas sensitisation due to a change in the physical conditions can only be perceptible when they are present in larger amounts. In the case of methyl alcohol the sensitisation observed is probably due to a complex formation with the non-electrolyte and the potential bearing ion on the surface of the colloid (*cf.* Kawjat, *Colloid J.* 1939, 8, 399). From the results in Tables II(A) and V(A) we find that there is sensitisation on the addition of methyl alcohol to both arsenious sulphide and ferric hydroxide sols and lowering in the adsorption of the oppositely charged ions. From this one may expect that sensitisation may be due to a complex formation with the non-electrolyte.

Freundlich (*loc. cit.*) on the other hand believes, as already stated, that protection is due to the encircling of the colloidal particle by a film of the lyophilic colloid which prevents flocculation.

Recently Pauli and Kitaj (*loc. cit.*) have suggested that protection is produced by the increase in the complex formed between the lyophobic colloid and the protective agent. They have further suggested that this may be brought about on the addition of neutral salts by an increased dissociation of the carboxyl groups.

From the results recorded in Tables III, IV(A & B), and VB, VI(A & B), it can be easily inferred that on increasing the concentration of the non-electrolyte there is no increase in the adsorption of the oppositely charged ions, on the contrary, there is a decrease in the adsorption. This means that no great electric charge is imparted for producing stability with ethyl alcohol, agar agar and gelatine and the non-electrolytes that have been used in the above tables, if the adsorption of the oppositely charged ion on coagulation is related to the charge on the colloid.

The adsorption in this paper has been measured at the coagulating concentrations which are different at different concentrations of the non-electrolytes. It is very likely that slight variations in the adsorption may take place due to this change in the concentration of the coagulating electrolyte but the entire change cannot be attributed to this, as in all the tables excepting Table II(A) the last three concentrations are the same but the amount adsorbed is not the same in any case.

The author's most sincere thanks are to Dr. A. C. Chatterji for his valuable suggestions and guidance in this work.